

INTERACTING WITH SONIFICATIONS: THE MESONIC FRAMEWORK FOR INTERACTIVE AUDITORY DATA SCIENCE

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces mesonic, a novel framework for cross-platform, back-end independent, pythonic sonification framework that encapsulates useful concepts such as the Timeline, Synth, Buffer, Event, and Playback into objects. Developed with use cases in mind from modern sonification and interactive sonification, specifically techniques such as audification, parameter mapping sonification and model-based sonification, the system provides lean, clear, and easy-to-read code for developing sonification systems. In this paper we lay out the foundations, present particular highlights and demonstrate mesonic with a handful of sonification examples. We deal with two types of interaction: (a) *code-level interaction*, which refers to the interaction with sonic-related objects for developers, i.e. *just-in-time* coding, allowing to inherit and modify structures quickly, and (b) *time-level interaction* with the sonification and sonification parameters, which refers to interactive sonification in a very original sense of its definition back in 2004. Finally (c) mesonic allows to persist sonifications in a Timeline, by which novel interactions are enabled through control of the navigation over the Timeline. The full project repository is provided on GitHub github.com/interactive-sonification/mesonic

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the beginning of modern sonification research back in 1992, researchers had to find ways to interconnect the following components: access to data, extraction of relevant or usable features, mappings or other algorithmic transformations towards (intermediate) representations that are useful for rendering (aka parameters), systems for sound computing/rendering, and finally technical systems to project the sound and thus close the loop to the researchers' own auditory system. But that's not the whole story: on top of that, interactive visualizations, (graphical) user interfaces and services such as functions to record and replay sonifications are required in order to enable a productive research process.

Looking at the large number of alternative solutions (see Sec. 2), there is clearly still no 'one size fits all' solution. In addition, with the advent of the field of interactive sonification (2004++) [1], more needs came in, from real-time data processing as in auditory biofeedback systems to interactive data selection and interactive parameter manipulation.

As researchers in the field of auditory display, we are often contacted by curious application-domain experts with the question what tools they could use to sonify their data – and the answer

so far often is that there is none that is apt for the sonification layperson, at least if it involves specifically tailored use cases for complex data.

How can we improve the situation? How can we learn from well-established and successful and highly capable visualization workflows to establish sonification counterparts that offer easy access for end users (such as `sonify(mydata, method="...", arguments="...")`)? Many would wish this also to come with ways to package code as apps with GUIs. But we rather focus on extensible parts, and in addition also think of sonification designers, programmers and developers, experts, who are eager to have powerful tool chains into which we can all contribute, so that we invest into a shared, open-source, flexible, well-maintained programming platform, ultimately all profiting from more shareable and reproducible research.

We tried hard to identify and combine all needs, requirements and wishes for such a system. Sometimes we called it 'the matplotlib of sonification', in recognition of how ubiquitous that famous Python package is in about anybody's data science routines and how well it encapsulates visualization methods.

On our path to that end, we came to realize that such a system will only be realizable on the shoulders of a solid framework that bridges the gap between the ultimately envisioned high-level system to the actual existing and powerful sound computing engines (which represent the 'low-level' as they are closer to the sample-to-sample coding of sound), hence it requires a middle – or *meso*-level system – to anchor 'rendering backends' into the programming language. With *mesonic*, we here present our solution for this problem, specifically for the popular programming language Python. On the way of defining it, we addressed a number of frequently encountered problems and requirements from sonification in general and Parameter-Mapping Sonification in particular. This paper also positions and discusses our contributions in the context of interactive sonification and addresses opportunities and challenges for mesonic to support interactive sonification use cases.

2. RELATED WORK ON AND ISSUES WITH SONIFICATION FRAMEWORKS

The need for specialized sonification software was first described by the Sonification Report [2], which is often regarded as a foundation of the scientific discipline. The report proposed a "sonification shell", that is build upon pre-existing realtime sound synthesis packages. The software should provide facilities for importing data, choosing transformations from values to sound and controlling the sonic output in sync with other media. The software

should be interactive and allow the user to conduct experiments. It was deemed that it is easy to get started with the sonification shell for novice researchers, while experts should be able to “tinker under the hood”.

Over the years of research, there were many sonification specific programs and toolkits created that allow the user to sonify their data. The variety of tools reflects the diversity of the sonification discipline. However, it seems that “sonification has not yet found its scientific champion” according to a review titled by Bearman and Brown [3]. The paper covered 51 articles from 2009 to 2012 and found that sonification specific tools do not get enough traction in the community. Bearman and Brown [3] found that synthesis tools are most popular for realizing the sonifications.

While this seems like a natural thing to do for experts, given the great control and expressiveness offered by the synthesis tools, it is also an obstacle for novice researchers, as they need to learn these often complex tools. This practice is even more questionable considering that Bearman and Brown [3] found that sonification researchers often use the same tools for all their sonifications instead of using different tools that could offer benefits in the different applications. This suggests that even domain experts are not willing to invest the time and effort to learn and use multiple synthesis tools.

A review of 32 publications [4]–[40] that feature 21 different software tools and applications for sonification was done. The tools reviewed focused directly on creating sonifications. Many tools have a clear focus toward a certain application. An example for this is the Sonification Sandbox [12]–[14] which focuses on the creation of Auditory Graphs and recently has been renamed to Highcharts Sonification Studio [15]. Another common ground of sonification tools is that they are mostly only shortly supported and become deprecated quite fast. An honorable exception is the aforementioned Sonification Studio [15]. The review also provided valuable insights into the changes that occurred in the tools between the different publications and the problems that were faced.

A common update was an increased modularity of the software and the separation into more independent parts, often with the intention to enable the integration of sonification into other software or to allow the usage of sound synthesis tools as part of the software [6], [13].

Other interesting insights were provided by the SonEnvir developers [16]–[18] who attempted to extend SuperCollider (SC) with data loading, processing and representation capabilities. However, in the third publication and after two years of work, it was noted that the project turned out to be rather complex and that only the data model was specified in greater detail and implemented. One should consider that SonEnvir was explicitly designed to be interdisciplinary and targeted many different sciences like neurology, theoretical physics, sociology and speech communication. Thus, the implementation of a data model in SC that allowed a unified representation and parsing of the different data types and the creation of specific sonification prototypes were quite an achievement.

This nicely demonstrates how sonification has to deal with sound synthesis and data handling, and both of these tasks are in fact a bottomless pit. Thus a high modularity should be a major goal of sonification tools as the reuse of software parts for both the sound synthesis and the data processing should boost productivity towards the transformation of the data into sound which is actually the defining part of the sonification.

3. FUNDAMENTAL CONCEPTS OF MESONIC

The most important concepts of the *mesonic* framework are introduced in the following sections. These concepts try to combine established and widely used constructs with novel ideas. The single ideas were motivated by the requirement of modularity discussed in Sec. 2 and aim to support the field of sonification by splitting a sonification into different parts and hence introducing a new terminology to talk and discuss about sonifications.

In the following section, the concepts of mesonic are described in detail and also related to existing concepts used by visualization software. The main audio concepts are explained in Sec. 3.1 and are based on ideas that are already used by many audio synthesis tools. These audio objects define actions, which are then scheduled using a Context (Sec. 3.2) and put as Event into a Timeline (Sec. 3.3). These are important and novel concepts in mesonic as they continue to make use of constructs known from visualizations and adapt them for the sonification domain to get a data structure that can be explicitly used to represent, manipulate and render the sonifications. How exactly the audio of the sonification is generated from these data structures is described in Sec. 3.4.

An overview of mesonic is shown in Fig. 1.

3.1. Object-oriented Interfaces for Audio

A core concept of mesonic is to allow the usage of multiple different audio backends, to increase the flexibility of sound synthesis offered by the framework. This requires to abstract the sound processing and synthesis into higher-level objects that can be implemented by the different backends. The resulting sound synthesis interfaces offer a meso-level as they are basically the primitives of a sonification which can be combined to form different sonification designs.

This can be compared to the approach found in visualization libraries, where a common example would be matplotlib’s [41] different usage layers. The user can create visualizations by simply using high-level plotting functions offered by pyplot or by using the object-oriented interface to manually build a visualization from the single components (Artists) of a figure¹. Note that these approaches are not separated, as the high-level functions also create and use the same objects to build a complex figure. This also means that other libraries can again be built on these parts and offer even more advanced high-level plotting functions, like e.g. the specialized data science visualizations created by Scikit-plot [42]. The single components also are the only concepts known by the backend that contain the information and functionality to render the visualization behind the scene.

This offers multiple benefits for visual as well as auditory representations of data. It allows using multiple backends depending on the current needs of the user and the available resources. A very important aspect is that users do not need to know the backend that is used to create the representation, as the backend is controlled through an abstract interface. And also, the backend does not need to know what exactly users might come up with, but rather does assemble the whole from simple primitives. An example for this is how a complex artwork can be drawn from multiple simple shapes.

The object-oriented approach also allows the user to tinker under the hood, as it is described by the Sonification Report [2]. A

¹matplotlib coding styles <https://matplotlib.org/stable/tutorials/introductory/usage.html#coding-styles> accessed 2022-06-23

Figure 1: A simplified overview of the responsibilities of the single objects of mesonic.

common use case is to create a representation e.g. with the pyplot interface using the high-level functions and then adjusting the resulting primitives using the object-oriented approach to further specify details such as the title of the figure.

Besides benefits for the user, the backend approach also offers multiple benefits for the development and runtime. One of the major benefits is that the complex sound processing capabilities of the pre-existing backends must not be reimplemented and are separated, which also allows distributed computing using multiple or real-time specialized machines [43].

The following sections describe the abstractions of sound synthesis used, called Synth (Sec. 3.1.1) and Buffer (Sec. 3.1.2). For recording the sound, mesonic also offers the Record concept described in Sec. 3.1.3. These concepts should be as simple as possible but still provide the user an already powerful set of tools to create many different sonifications as well as a new way to discuss them. However, it should be noted that there might in future be additional concepts or extensions of these concepts, as the mesonics framework is open for discussion and improvements.

3.1.1. Synth

The most important concept is the Synth. It is a concept that is already widely spread in audio synthesis and can be found e.g. in SuperCollider (SC) or under the name Instrument in Csound. Therefore, the Synth seems like an ideal high-level concept to built upon pre-existing sound synthesis software, like it is suggested by the Sonification Report [2]. The Synth concept describes a sound source that can be controlled in time and that can offer several properties such as the frequency or amplitude of an oscillator as parameters to control the sound synthesis. However, also creation

of Synths with ecological (perceptual) parameters is possible. It is based on a Synth declaration that defines the audio processing, often in terms of a specific combination of Unit Generators (UGens) under a specific Synth name.

The Synth can be instantiated multiple times in the backend using its unique name. For this, the backend should check if the name is known and then create the Synth instance and the respective parameters. To create new Synths descriptions, the backend should be directly used. This offers the user the full power and flexibility of the backend and keeps the sound synthesis separated from the transformation. The different backends should implement similar or the same Synths that have been evaluated and designed to be perceptually sensible using the same names. However, the instance creation should remain dynamic and adapt to the specific Synths supported by the backend and their implementation.

In mesonic, the Synth control possibilities are kept very simple and offer just the following actions:

start and stop control the lifetime of the sound of the Synth instance. The start action allows the creation of the instance and also to provide the initial values for the parameters. The stop action is for destroying the instance.

pause and resume are very similar to the stop and start actions with the difference that the instance will not be destroyed by the pause action, but only the sound will be stopped. The resume action then uses the stored state to let the sound continue from the time where it was paused. This might be used when the Synths play a longer sound, for instance, an audio recording.

set is used to control the parameters after the initial start action. It allows changing the parameter values. The available pa-

parameters should allow defining further data like the default value or which values are allowed, and the set control action should check and verify that the new value for the parameter is valid.

To give the user a way to rapidly spawn multiple instances of one Synth, an important differentiation has been made: the distinction of *mutable* and *immutable* Synths was found by ourselves to be practical in common use cases, and is also suggested by the research of Enge, Rind, Iber, *et al.* [44] who suggest the adaption of theoretical constructs from visualization to sonification.

mutable Synths directly represent a single synth or instrument instance in the backend and provides the user the full control with all commands mentioned above of this single instance. However, this means that a mutable Synth can't be started if it is already running, and it also might burden the user with management of the Synth's lifetime. This behavior is useful for creating continuous Parameter Mapping Sonifications (PMSons), where a continuous sound is modulated using sound parameters computed from the data. Conceptually, this creates the 1D auditory mark, which resembles the auditory equivalent of the 1D visual mark also known as 'line' [44].

immutable Synths on the other hand, are not tightly coupled to one backend synth. This allows to create multiple overlapping, with the drawback that the immutable Synth does only support the start command. This means that an immutable Synth instance, as the name suggests, cannot be changed once spawned. This requires from the instance to manage its own lifetime, as it cannot be directly addressed after the creation in order to set parameters or stop it. This behavior is useful for creating discrete PMSons where often short sound events are used which might overlap each other. Whereas mutable Synths can also be used for this use-case, it would require the user to create a mutable Synth for each sound event, or to keep track of currently playing instances and already finished instances that could then be reused for a new sound event. According to Enge, Rind, Iber, *et al.* [44] this can be related to the 0D auditory mark, which is the equivalent of the 0D visual mark also known as 'point'.

The current Synth concept is designed to be very simple in order to reduce the needed requirements of the backend and should allow to quickly develop and contribute additional backends. The grouping of certain actions e.g. is solely based on the same execution time. The Synths do not directly interact with each other. This simple design should not only reduce the development time and requirements for additional backends but also could scaffold the creation of meaningful Synths that are shared and evaluated by experts.

3.1.2. Buffer

The Buffer is also a common audio concept and typically stores audio snippets such as samples or recordings. The Buffer interface should provide a unified way to load audio data from a file or directly from provided data into the backend and make it available to use. Besides the creation of the Buffer itself, the backend should also support the creation of one or multiple Synths from a Buffer. This Synth can then be used to playback the data. Different backends will most likely offer different Synths with features like granular synthesis. The creation of a Synth using a Buffer in

the backend also allows the dynamic creation of an object in the backend that is specifically adapted to the provided Buffer and the demanded features. This is required e.g. in SuperCollider (SC), where certain information such as the number of channels is often needed at the time of the SC Synth Definition.

3.1.3. Record

The Record concept allows the user to record the audio output of the backend and represents a single audio recording that will be when finished saved into a file. The controls of the Record are similar to the controls of the Synth concept.

start and stop control the start and end time of the Record. When the Record is stopped, the backend should create the audio file and then mark the Record as finished.

pause and resume allow the user to temporarily disable the recording of the audio. The audio file will not contain the audio from the pause command to the resume command.

3.2. Context

The Context concept could be seen as the auditory counterpart of the Figure known from matplotlib and is quite similar to the AudioContext from the Web Audio API. As the name suggests, it provides the context to the other concepts.

It allows creating instances of the concepts and provides a logical belonging for them. This means that e.g. a Record created by a certain Context instance should record the audio output of the Synths belonging to the same Context. As a result of this, the user that wants to create a sonification should always create a Context first, which then enables the usage of the other concepts. Accordingly, the Context defines the domain of possible actions in terms of the concepts noted above, because the Context contains all the different parts that specify what actions are available.

Besides allowing the user to specify the domain of possible actions, it is also responsible for the *sonification time*. The Synth, Buffer and Record concepts define only *what* can be done but not *when* it will be done. This very important information is added by the Context. The Context allows the user to set a time, which will then be used e.g. when the start action of a Synth in this Context is triggered. To store the time together with an action, the Context stores a Timeline with Events, which is explained in Sec. 3.3.

Along with the Timeline, the Context does contain all the single parts of the sonification and also stores what actions happen in time. This makes the Context an ideal central interface for operations concerning the whole Context, like the creation of a non-realtime rendering, which requires the information what to do and when to do it. This is similar to a scene graph or a matplotlib Figure, which also contain the single parts of a visualization with their locations in space and allow rendering the visualization. Using the terminology of Enge, Rind, Iber, *et al.* [44], that the time is the substrate of the sonification like the space is the substrate of the visualization, this introduces the Context as counterpart of the Figure or Scene and allows building a further bridge between sonification and visualization concepts.

3.3. Timeline and Events

The object-oriented concepts do not directly trigger actions in the backend, but produce Events (Sec. 3.3.2). The Events will be scheduled in the time domain using the Timeline (Sec. 3.3.1). This

means that the Timeline is the connection between Event generating concepts (Sec. 3.1) such as Synth or Record and the Event consuming rendering concepts (Sec. 3.4) in the backend. The Event defines the actual information which is shared between the frontend and backend.

3.3.1. Timeline

The Timeline as such is a novel concept for sonification software. The idea to represent a sonification as a data structure is inspired by the scene graph often used in graphical programs and also influenced by the work of Satyanarayan, Russell, Hoffswell, *et al.* [45], which describes the data flow architecture of Reactive Vega.

A scene graph is a data structure that stores the single graphical objects as nodes in a spatial and logical hierarchy, like a tree or graph structure. This allows improved control and manipulation of the graphics, since single nodes are grouped and can e.g. be rotated or otherwise transformed using the scene graph. It also can boost the performance of algorithms like ray tracing that use the hierarchical structure to quickly determine the bounding boxes of objects that need to be rendered and what parts of the scene can be skipped.

mesonic takes the concept of the scene graph and adapts it to the context of sonifications with the result of the Timeline. The Timeline provides a data structure that consists of multiple collections of Events that are located in time. Such a collection of Events with a timepoint is called Time-Bundle. It contains all the Events of the audio concepts such as a Synth start or a Record stop that should be executed at the time point of the Time-Bundle by the backend.

A sonification needs time to unfold, therefore a Timeline should consist of multiple Time-Bundles. These are sorted according to their time, which allows the audio rendering to consume the Timeline in order. The Timeline should be a representation of the complete sonification and thus should also store additional data needed like the start and end time of the sonification.

3.3.2. Event

The Event is similar to the node in the scene graph. It will also be processed by the rendering process and then presented to the user. Multiple events create a sonification like multiple objects in a scene graph create a visualization. The Events describe a certain action of the audio concepts that can be processed and executed by an Event Handler in the backend. Typically, the Events in the Timeline are Synth Events that reflect the control actions (start, stop, pause, resume, set) from Synth objects (Sec. 3.1.1) or the similar control actions created by Record objects (Sec. 3.1.3). An example to describe the data stored in an Event is the Synth Event that contains the following information:

Event Type This information defines what kind of Event was produced and in the Example of the Synth concept what control action should be triggered in the backend.

Event Values that contain values for the action, such as the audio parameters of a Synth start or set action.

The Event is a simple object, which merely stores data about an action. Nevertheless, an Event allows defining custom behavior, because it can be used for arbitrary actions. Examples for this might be *plotting Events* used to control a synchronized visualization, as the Event Handler does not need to be part of the audio

backend. An Event Handler could trigger arbitrary functions that e.g. highlight the data points that are currently sonified. Hence, an Event should always provide all the information needed to the Handler. And it should also be noted that an Event does not need to come from another Object, but could be manually created by the user. Besides the data describing the action directly, the Event stores also further data such as the Track and possible Metadata.

Tracks Additionally to the ability to group Events in time as Time-Bundles, the user can also specify a Track for each Event generating object. The Track is simply an additional identifier and thus allows grouping events by their sources. The Track ID can then be used to change the processing of the Events by e.g. filtering all Event from a certain Track or e.g. adjusting the amplitude values of the Synths on Track 1. This concept of tracks is known from DAWs and can be compared to the layer concept found in the scene graph that also allows the grouping of objects.

Metadata To provide the Event Handler even more information, the metadata of an Event can be specified. The metadata can e.g. contain a data identifier that would allow the Event Handler to recognize the origin of the event and thus could filter the events based on data properties. It would also be possible to use the metadata to provide the Event Handler all the information needed to perform a just-in-time calculation of the Event values and also to trigger certain callbacks.

3.4. Event Processing and Rendering

As explained in Sec. 3.3 the Timeline and Events are used to save the sonification as a data structure. These data can be understood as a kind of musical score and should be usable by the different audio backends of mesonic to render the sonification. This can be done in an interactive fashion using the Playback (Sec. 3.4.1) or in non-realtime by using the NRT (non-realtime) rendering (Sec. 3.4.3). How single Time-Bundles and included Events can be preprocessed will be explained in Sec. 3.4.2

3.4.1. Playback

The Playback is focused on real-time rendering and providing an interactive experience for the user. The Playback could be seen as sonification adaptation of the Camera Pattern from information visualization [46], as the Playback also allows the user to affect the way the sounds are rendered and get multiple different “auditory views” from the same “auditory scene graphs” (Timeline).

For this, the Playback keeps track of the current time and the respective Time-Bundle and triggers the Event Handlers when the time point is reached. This can be realized, e.g. with a separate worker thread and a pointer to the next Time-Bundle that keeps checking how much time has passed between the current time point provided by a clock and the fixed starting time reference to see if the Time-Bundle needs to be scheduled for execution. The execution is explained in Sec. 3.4.2. The Playback worker thread should also check for changes of the Timeline and adjust the pointer to the next Time-Bundle accordingly.

To facilitate interactivity, the Playback allows the user to control the Timeline playback similar to a CD-Player as it can be started, stopped, as well as paused, and resumed. Besides the control of the state of the Playback, the user can control the rate of the sonification time. Thus, the user can scale the time and can e.g. fit a long Timeline into a short period of time or extend the time,

which enables us to listen to the Events more slowly. However, it should be noted that this is only effecting the control actions that are stored in the Events and not the synthesis itself. This means that the frequencies of a Synth e.g. do not change, but the musical score is played slower. By using negative rates, the user can also reverse the Timeline which then will change the start Synth Events into stop Synth Events in the case of mutable Synths and adapting set Synth Events in such a way that the previous value will be set instead of the new one. In the case of immutable Synths, the start Events do remain unchanged. It is also possible to set the time during playback and thus allows the user to jump in time and to listen e.g. to the last 5 seconds again. Lastly, the user can also use the Playback to loop over the Timeline. For this the user needs to enable the looping feature and then the Playback automatically jumps from the end time to the start time of the loop minus the duration of the loop. All the three parameters of the loop can be set using the Playback.

To allow this interactivity, the time calculation is realized using an approach which defines different sections of time. A time section will always begin if the Playback changes. Besides starting, stopping, pausing and resuming the Playback also the change of the rate and a time jump will trigger the beginning of a new section. The Playback time that provides the current time of the Playback with respect to all the changes of the rate and state can then be calculated using the following formula

$$\mathbf{time} = \mathbf{duration}_{\text{section}} * \mathbf{rate} + \mathbf{offset}$$

Where **rate** denotes the current Playback rate, which can be positive or negative and scales the duration of the section $\mathbf{duration}_{\text{section}}$ calculated by

$$\mathbf{duration}_{\text{section}} = \mathbf{tp}_{\text{current}} - \mathbf{tp}_{\text{section}}$$

$\mathbf{tp}_{\text{current}}$ denotes the current time as time point from the used clock and $\mathbf{tp}_{\text{section}}$ is the section time point that saves the time point of the beginning of the section and is updated with the value of the current time point $\mathbf{tp}_{\text{current}}$ if a new section starts. The **offset** will be updated to the time of the beginning of the section, which would be the old **time** in the case of a rate change. One could imagine that the **time** is a linear combination of all the section times where the rates of the sections are used as scalars and the old linear combination is saved as **offset**. In the case of a time jump, the **offset** will be set to the target of this time jump and thus resetting the linear combination.

3.4.2. Event processing

The Bundle Processor concept is responsible for the processing of the Time-Bundles and should be used by the Playback and the NRT Rendering. Besides splitting the different Event types included in a single Time-Bundle and passing them to the respective Event Handler in the backend, the Bundle Processor should also be responsible for filtering the Events. As already explained in Sec. 3.3.2 the Events can be filtered according to their Track and the additional event metadata. For this, it should be possible to let the user define a custom filter and or transformation function which is applied to each Event. With this function, it is possible to recalculate the whole Event or discard it. However, it should be noted that this will happen just before the actual scheduled execution time that the Timeline provided and during the latency time of the Bundle Processor. The latency time is added to the scheduled execution time, thus it should be set high enough for this additional

processing and the latency of the backend. This means there is a tradeoff between advanced processing and actual realtime sonification as complex Event processing might add a significant latency to the sonification.

3.4.3. Non-realtime Rendering

For non-realtime (NRT) rendering, one can simply provide the Context that contains the complete Timeline with all the Events and the corresponding event creating (audio) objects to the backend. The audio backend can then use the information stored in the objects to prepare the backend to handle the Events from these objects. It should be noted that NRT rendering is only possible for the Events in the Timeline that are known to the used backend, this means that any Events which cannot be handled by the backend will be discarded. Additional preprocessing steps, such as the filtering of Events by the Track, can be achieved by using the Bundle Processor explained in Sec. 3.4.2. After this preparation, the backend should be able to process all the Time-Bundles according to their time point and the Events contained from the Timeline.

The rendering result is saved as a sound file containing the sonification. This should allow processing very large Timelines, as it is possible to preprocess the timeline to create multiple smaller Timelines and later append the resulting audio or make other backend specific optimization using the Timeline. To create for example a multimedia NRT rendering that includes an animation and a sonification the user could write a visual backend that processes the visual Events and then renders the animation. The two render artifacts should then be combined to get the complete multimedia render. In the future, such visual Events and backends could become a part of the mesonic framework.

4. SONIFICATION EXAMPLES

In this section we demonstrate how to use mesonic for selected use-cases in the area of auditory display, specifically Audification, Parameter- Mapping Sonification and Model-based Sonification. We provide as supplementary material Jupyter notebooks that allow to investigate the different interaction levels (code-based/time-based) hands-on and to provide a starting point for own designs. Further details and examples can be seen at our GitHub and in our documentation² in the notebooks section as due to the limited space we can here only discuss the most important aspects of these methods.

4.1. Audification

With mesonic, Audification can easily be achieved by filling a buffer from data and playing it through a Synth capable of using a Buffer as waveform. In mesonic, after the data has been loaded (shown in the first four lines of code), an Audification is created via the final two lines of code:

```
import mesonic, numpy
context = mesonic.create_context()
context.enable_realtime();

data = numpy.loadtxt("./files/eeg.csv",
                    delimiter=",")
```

²mesonic documentation <https://mesonic.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

```
buf = context.buffers.from_data(data[:, [0, 1]],
                               sr=256)
```

```
buf_synth = context.synths.from_buffer(buf)
buf_synth.start(rate=20)
```

Data is loaded via `numpy.loadtxt`, the sampling rate needs to be specified when creating the buffer. However, SuperCollider buffers only deal with integer numbers here. Note that we use the default synth here to play a Buffer, which provides (among others) a `rate` argument to replay the Buffer in time-compressed or stretched in time. Note that via the channel selection (here `data[:, [0, 1]]`) the buffer will be set up as stereo buffer, so on playback sound will routed to the first two output channels.

The following example shows an interactive audification, using a granular synthesis with controllable position using a custom synthesizer. It is useful to set `context.processor.latency = 0.05` to reduce interaction latency. With the following synth definition

```
context.synths.buffer_synthdefs["tgaud"] = r"""
{ | bufnum={BUFNUM}, amp=0.3, rate=10,
  trate=5, pos=0 |
  var dur, cpos, sig;
  dur = 4 / trate;
  cpos = pos * BufDur.kr(bufnum);
  sig = TGrains.ar(2, Impulse.ar(trate),
  bufnum, rate, cpos, dur, 0, 0.5, 2);
  Out.ar(0, sig * amp);
}"""
```

we define a custom Synth to be used for interacting with Buffers. An instance is created using `tgsyn = context.synths.from_buffer(buf, synth_name="tgaud")` and started simply using `tgsyn.start()`. On execution of that line, we hear some sound but no progression in time as the position `pos` is kept constant. Code-level interaction is achieved by assigning other values, e.g. `tgsyn.pos = 0.5`. However, it would be nicer to directly control the position and other arguments via slider widgets, which can be achieved for instance using a custom function and IPython widgets

```
def explore_tgrain(trate=20, rate=50, pos=0,
                  amp=0.5):
    tgsyn.rate = rate
    tgsyn.trate = trate
    tgsyn.pos = pos
    tgsyn.amp = amp
```

```
from ipywidgets import interactive, widgets
interactive(explore_tgrain, trate=(1,100,1),
           rate=(0.2,250,0.05), pos=(0,1,0.001),
           amp=(0,1,0.01))
```

Now we can scrub interactively through the data to detect and explore any patterns.

The supplementary material continues to demonstrate how – instead of slider widgets – controls can additionally and easily be connected to dragging the (left-clicked) Mouse pointer over a data plot, allowing to interactively understand how visual patterns and sonification relate. While this is nothing fundamentally new or innovative, the point here is that this can be achieved with few lines of code, thus resulting in short, readable, and flexibly modifiable, i.e. customizable and extensible specifications of interactive sonifications.

4.2. Parameter Mapping Sonification

Discrete Parameter Mappings usually process a data set row-wise and map features of the data to onset and other parameters of sonic events. In turn, it is favorable to disable the realtime interaction via `context.disable_realtime()`. Then the temporal coherence within the rendition is assured. The following minimal example illustrates that little boilerplate code ‘pollutes’ the specification of a mapping. For simplicity, we use the same data set as before (more precisely 4 arbitrarily selected columns).

```
duration = 3
sel = slice(2100, 2456)
plt.scatter(data[sel, 2], data[sel, 5],
            s=50*data[sel, 12]+25)
pb = context.create_playback()
for r in data[sel]:
    onset = linlin(r[2], -1, 1, 0, duration)
    with context.at(onset): # provides time
        sli.start(
            freq = midicps(linlin(r[5], -1, 1, 50, 90)),
            dur = linlin(r[12], -1, 1, 0.01, 0.4),
            pan = linlin(r[3], -1, 1, -1, 1),
            amp = 0.05
        )
pb.start(rate=1)
```

With the last line, the playback can be started – and restarted with other temporal scaling using the rate parameter. While a playback proceeds, the rate can also be interactively changed, and the direction reversed using negative values.

A continuous parameter mapping, instead, requires mutable synths, yet the code is equally straightforward (cf. supplementary material).

If needed, the automatic time advance (via playback) can be foregone to couple parameter setting directly to a Mouse interaction, as shown in the Jupyter notebook. The included example plots a 6D time series and allows the user to scrub over the plot using the pressed left Mouse button, mapping series data to a spectral deviation around the channel-specific center frequency. Furthermore, the Mouse pointer’s y-coordinate is used to pronounce specific channels by attenuating channels that are vertically distant from the Mouse y-level in the plot. The synth is:

```
scn.SynthDef("dynklang", r"""
{ |out=0, f0=100, amp=0.1,
  freqs=#[1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10],
  amps=#[0,0,0,0,0,0,0,0,0,0]|
  Out.ar(out, amp * DynKlang.ar(`[freqs, amps,
  0!10], freqscale: f0)!2);
}""").add()
```

and the core part of the mapping

```
def on_move(event):
    if event.inaxes and event.button is
    MouseButton.LEFT:
        vec = dd[int(event.xdata * sr), :dim]
        ampsvec = np.exp(-((event.ydata -
        np.arange(0, ofs*dim, ofs))/sigma)**2)
        sdk.amps = list(ampsvec)
        midis = np.arange(dim)*10+40
            + linlin(vec, -1, 1, -5, 5)
        sdk.freqs = list(midicps(midis))
```

Again, the code for integrating interactive PMSon into the visualization (here: matplotlib plot) is compact, so that developers can focus on their designs.

4.3. Model-based Sonification

The clarity and readability of code that mesonic offers also assists the specification of sonification models. Due to limited space we merely refer to the example notebook mesonic-mbs.ipynb that can be found in the documentation³. The example demonstrates how the data sonogram sonification model can be implemented as a class using the mesonic building blocks. It thus provides a template for similarly structured excitatory interactive models and also demonstrates how mesonic can be used to craft higher level interfaces as the complete data sonogram is created by a single line like `DataSonogram(context, df, x="flipper_length_mm", y="body_mass_g", label="species")`

4.4. The path towards high-level sonification interfaces

With mesonic as a meso-level framework to mediate between the lower end (sound-computing) and higher end (application-specific and design-oriented needs, we foresee as a next step the creation of a library that encapsulates sonification methods in high-level functions such as `audify(data, rate, mode, **kwargs)` and `pmson(data, synth, mapping, kind='discrete', **kwarg)`, and so on, all coming with heuristics that make them applicable out of the box for the novice users and configurable. For expert users the underlying source code should be easy to understand and copy as starting point for special designs. Yet this endeavor is subject to current and future work to be reported elsewhere.

5. DISCUSSION

With mesonic we introduced the usage of multiple different levels of control for sonification with a focus on the intermediate (meso) level. By using a series of audio interfaces that provide an abstraction of low-level audio processing in the backend, we aimed at and achieved independence from the actual complexity of sound processing and rendering. The idea was to offer control of the synthesis by using only simple actions from easy to understand concepts. We believe that this indeed makes the sonification process more transparent and lowers the entry barrier for novice researchers, yet we cannot support this yet by empirical evidence but only speak from our subjective experience. The lower entry barrier is especially important as it seems often to be too hard to learn new tools, as even experts stick to their own tools [3].

The object-oriented abstractions provide a meso-level as they provide a lower level to talk about sonifications than the known sonification techniques like Parameter Mapping Sonification, but are still more abstract than the actual audio synthesis used in the backend. This is influenced by the common idea in visualization that the different types of visualizations consists of elementary parts that are easy to plot but as a whole are able to represent complex information.

However, the proposed audio objects also introduce certain constraints. We argue that we need certain constraints as they enable us to structure the sonification and realize it with regards of technical aspects. An example for this is the Buffer, which in mesonic is *static* and does not offer additional actions that

e.g. change data in the Buffer via the Events. This design decision is based on the finding that such operations often can not be performed in real-time and are often quite backend-specific. We suggested to use other libraries such as `pya` [47], which focuses on working with audio signals, to prepare signals before loading them into a mesonic Buffer. Another idea to alleviate constraints is to create separate concepts such as Stream or Bus, which could be introduced as dynamic counterpart to the Buffer. However, the Synth concept should be the favorable – and in most cases sufficient – tool to generate sound dynamically.

The focus of mesonic has *not* been to offer the “one size fits all” solution in terms of a high-level sonification application, but instead to create a framework upon which others can build their work. More so, mesonic aims to focus on the interconnection and reuse of the existing parts from data to sound processing and does provide the user an abstract level to define and control sonifications. It thus provides the basis for defining and building advanced tools, such as high-level libraries that allow users to simply call one of many available functions to create sophisticated sonifications. But mesonic is not limited to that: the creation of specialized applications that suit the specific needs of a given use case and data domain should also be possible to realize.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have introduced mesonic. The framework makes the following key contributions to the area of software tools in sonification research: (a) it clearly separates the different steps of the sonification pipeline into the data processing, audio synthesis and actual sonification transformations steps in order to allow the integration of different specialized tools into a complete sonification toolkit. (b) it provides new abstractions which allow representing the sonification that is based on common elements found in sound synthesis but also by novel concepts inspired by the visualization domain. The object-oriented approach allowed an easy implementation and should facilitate new discussion about the elements of sonification itself. (c) it fosters interaction on different levels, allowing to close the loop during design, (i) by enabling code-level interactions such as adjusting mappings while the sonification playing or at least in quick cycles, (ii) by making it straight-forward and easy to connect graphical interfaces such as IPython widgets in the Jupyter Notebook to parameters that affect mappings or aspects of the sonification, and (iii) by facilitating the direct embedding of sonification into available visualization systems in the data science community, such as matplotlib and others.

Mesonic has been developed as open-source software on GitHub and follows common Python development guidelines. It will be made available via PyPI, and should work on most platforms.

As future work, we see particular benefit in the establishing of additional backends such as for MAX/MSP, Csound, PureData or WebAudio. The latter one might be strategic for the path towards turning mesonic into a web-compatible platform, running mesonic via PyScript in the browser. We are eager to serve the community and hear your feedback and needs to guide the future development.

³Model-Based Sonification using mesonic <https://mesonic.readthedocs.io/en/latest/notebooks/mesonic-mbs.html>

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